

TITLE

Deep Insight Representations using Recurring Revenue Management System

Name of Applicants

**Dr. Amol Gawande
Dr. Atul Kumar
Dr. Vinaydeep Brar**

Name of Authors

**Dr. Amol Gawande
Dr. Atul Kumar
Dr. Vinaydeep Brar**

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Amol Gawande', is written over a faint circular stamp.

Deep Insight Representations using Recurring Revenue Management System

Introduction:

As the business ecosystem has shifted their business strategies to the recurring revenue management system, as customers are increasingly preferring to pay for access rather than ownership. Many industries have moved from the one-time sales model to the recurring revenue model, which enables companies to generate consistent revenue by providing continuous fetch their items in exchange of regularly scheduled payments. Interestingly, such business model is no longer limited to magazine, music, and movie subscriptions. Now it is becoming prevalent in domains as varied as software, cars, groceries, clothing, and furniture.

Take the example of the automotive industry, where customers can now subscribe to cars as a service instead of buying them outright. Offered by popular brands like Audi, Porsche, and Nissan, car subscriptions generally include everything - the car, insurance, and maintenance cost are combined into a single monthly fee. Unlike a traditional lease, here the customer has the option to easily switch cars during their subscription. The model benefits automakers by creating an additional channel for predictable revenue and allowing them to quickly adapt to changing customer demands. With attractive benefits such as steady cash flow and high customer retention, the recurring revenue business model is here to stay.

Objective: The business style has been moved towards the different paradigm, which is called recurring revenue which can be defined as a revenue model in a organization which earn money by providing their services to the users in a certain amount on regular basis. Following are the significant approach of this recurring revenue model:

- Customer attraction and satisfaction for product or Services
- Change the recurring insight strategy
- Recurring Business Model

Technology Used for Recurring Revenue management system

Need of Recurring Revenue Model: Following are the significant key takeaways for the recurring revenue management system.

- Scheduled Revenue
- Increase Customer base
- Customer retention
- Low price and customer satisfaction
- Easy to access

Recurring revenue business management method:

In the business ecosystem this revenue model where the vendor provides access to a product or service in exchange for a recurring fee charged at scheduled intervals (monthly, quarterly, or yearly). This model forms the basis for subscription companies and membership services. Since customers are constantly buying the product or service month after month, predictable cash flow and a sustainable profit margin are guaranteed for the business. Unlike traditional one-off sales where the supplier-customer relationship ends after a single sale, the recurring revenue business model helps establish a deeper relationship with customers to achieve high customer retention.

Types of Recurring Revenue Models:

1. **Billing as per Usage:** In this model Customers are billed for their usage on a regular schedule like monthly.

A good example of this kind of recurring revenue model is a prepaid or postpaid mobile bill of any telecommunication organization.

Advantage: Saves the customer money when there's irregular usage. It's good value for low to mid-volume users.

Drawback: Unpredictable revenue for the business because of customer usage fluctuations, and unpredictable and surprising costs for customers. It may not provide good value for high volume customers.

Who it works for: Usage based models work best for businesses that can easily track usage whether it's the number of emails/messages/invoices sent, APIs used or triggers

ivated.

2. **Service-based billing:** In this model Customers are billed for their service selection or package like monthly or yearly.

Advantage: More predictable revenue and scales well for large/enterprise teams. There's no need to track usage.

Drawback: It can serve as a barrier for budget teams that will limit the number of seats to control costs. It doesn't always align with the value of the product, in which case it will leave money on the table. For example, a customer may end up paying for users who are not active. Slack addresses this issue by adding prorated credits for users who have become inactive in a billing cycle and only charge for active use.

Works for: User-based billing works best for team collaboration or customer service tools.

3. **Billing by tiers:** In this model, prices are created in "tiers". Each tier is designed for a specific user or buyer and is priced limited. Once a user reaches a limit at a particular level, they are upgraded to the next level that offers more functionality or usage.

Advantage: It allows you to appeal to a wide range of users and their specific needs, so there is something for everyone. It also helps companies understand where customers see the most value.

Drawback: Something for everyone is not always a good bet, because it has the potential to get lengthy and complicated very quickly.

Works for: It is most used by companies offering marketing or sales products.

4. **Hybrid billing:** as the name reflects this model, a mixed approach is adopted, choosing aspects of two or more revenue models, for example, many companies opt for hybrid prices, where they reach specific levels of use or number of users it will require you to upgrade to the next level. plan.

Advantage: It is a flexible way to structure prices, it allows companies to overcome the disadvantages of a single model by providing more nuanced prices that align with value.

Drawback: It can bring more complexity, so companies must go the extra mile to keep their hybrid models simple enough for everyone to understand.

It works for: In this, saas companies where the value that customers get from the product service does not clearly fit any model.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Munish', written over a faint circular stamp.

5. **Freemium:** In this, company provides the free access of service with limited features to the customers and consumer can use it as unpaid but if they require services with all features, the user can opt company subscription so this is how company earn money.

Fig1. Versions of Revenue Model

Types of businesses that are best suited for the recurring revenue model:

Although companies in many different industries have transformed to fit the recurring revenue model, there are certain types of companies that are particularly suitable for this business model.

1. **Content-based:** This type of companies that provide access to multimedia content, such as audio, video and books, have very successfully adopted the recurring revenue model, for example, Netflix, HBO and Spotify. Here the user subscribes to these services, registers to enjoy access to the services exclusively.
2. **Service-based:** In this business, several software companies offer access to their applications by subscription (SaaS) instead of one-time sales. SaaS eliminates the cost of initial software setup and the difficulty of implementing product updates for example, LinkedIn premium memberships and many more memberships from other multinationals.
3. **Product-based:** In this case, the product-based subscription model is subscription boxes, where customers sign up to receive boxes of a particular type of product at scheduled intervals (weekly, monthly, or quarterly). Based on demand, these boxes are roughly classified into two types: convenience and cured.

as of the recurring revenue management system:

While the recurring revenue model has grown in popularity, it is not without its challenges. Much can still go wrong if customer requirements, products, and competitive factors are not managed well.

1. Attrition management:

It is a common problem that all subscription companies face. It can go from a minor problem to a major challenge if the business cannot retain the majority of its customers and the churn rate spirals out of control.

2. Underwriting fatigue:

Subscription fatigue occurs when customers feel overwhelmed and tired of subscribing to many subscriptions. The explosion of subscription services has provided customers with numerous options in many industries. While it's nice to have options, recent studies reveal that too many options eventually create subscription fatigue, causing customers to cancel their subscriptions.

Conclusion:

The recurring revenue business model has become an attractive option for both customers and business owners. With its different types adopted across various business domains, the recurring income business model is gaining enormous popularity. However, like any business model, the recurring revenue model is not without its challenges. So when implemented correctly, the recurring revenue model can help you forecast revenue, plan for growth, expand your market, retain more customers, and ultimately improve your profits.

References:

- <https://www.netsuite.com/portal/products/erp/financial-management/revenue-management/recurring-revenue-management.shtml#:~:text=A%20predictable%2C%20recurring%20revenue%20stream,your%20customers%20and%20their%20interactions.>
- <https://jp.zuora.com/guides/recurring-revenue-management-for-optimization/>
- <https://www.bspny.com/solutions-recurring-revenue>

